

COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS ON HALF-HEUSLER SEMICONDUCTOR ALLOYS (COVSN): PROPERTIES, APPLICATION, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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Abstract: Half-Heusler semiconductor alloys have emerged as a compelling class of materials renowned for their extraordinary electronic, thermoelectric, and magnetic properties. This research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of Half-Heusler alloys, encompassing their crystal structure, electronic band properties, physical characteristics, synthesis methodologies, and potential applications. Computational simulations employing Wien2k software and DFT (Density Functional Theory) have been utilized extensively to elucidate these properties. These alloys, typically denoted by the chemical formula XYZ where X, Y, and Z represent different elements, exemplify the versatility of composite materials. Specifically, the CoVSn alloy, comprising cobalt (Co), vanadium (V), and tin (Sn), showcases synergistic properties that surpass those of its individual constituents. The crystal structure of Half-Heusler alloys, often cubic with XYZ ordering, contributes to their robust mechanical stability and favorable electronic band structures for various applications in solid-state electronics and thermoelectric devices. Moreover, their tunable electronic properties, dictated by the choice and arrangement of constituent elements, offer a promising avenue for designing materials with tailored functionalities. Advances in synthesis techniques, including vacuum arc melting and spark plasma sintering, have enabled precise control over alloy composition and microstructure, further enhancing their applicability in high-performance electronic and energy conversion devices. Ongoing research continues to explore novel Half-Heusler compositions and nanostructuring approaches to optimize their thermoelectric efficiency and magnetic properties, promising breakthroughs in sustainable energy and advanced electronics.

Index Terms - Half-Heusler Alloy, Thermo-electric Material, Semiconductor Alloy, Composite Material.

[1] INTRODUCTION

Half-Heusler semiconductor alloys, exemplified by CoVSn, represent a class of materials with remarkable potential across multiple technological domains due to their versatile properties. This paper provides an in-depth examination of CoVSn alloys, encompassing their thermal, mechanical, structural, and electronic characteristics, as well as exploring their diverse applications and future trajectories. At the core of our analysis lies the utilization of Wien2k software and DFT (Density Functional Theory), offering a sophisticated framework to probe the intricate behaviors of CoVSn alloys under varying conditions. Leveraging DFT capabilities within Wien2k, we unravel the thermal and electrical transport properties crucial for understanding the thermoelectric performance of CoVSn, essential for applications in waste heat recovery and energy

harvesting. Furthermore, Wien2k enables us to delve into the mechanical response of CoVSn alloys under different loading conditions, facilitating insights into their structural integrity and suitability for engineering applications in harsh environments. By simulating stress-strain relationships and deformation mechanisms, we aim to elucidate the mechanical robustness of CoVSn for applications spanning from structural materials to micro electromechanical systems (MEMS) [1].

Additionally, our simulations using Wien2k provide a comprehensive exploration of the electronic properties of CoVSn, including the electronic band structure, density of states, and charge carrier mobility. These insights are vital for understanding the behavior of CoVSn in electronic and spintronic devices, paving the way for innovations in fields such as semiconductor electronics and magnetic storage. Through the integration of Wien2k simulation work, this paper aims to offer a holistic understanding of CoVSn half-Heusler semiconductor alloys, laying the groundwork for their widespread adoption in various technological applications and contributing to the advancement of materials science and engineering.

Figure-: Half-Heusler Alloy. From Wanxiang et al. Ref. [3]

[2] COMPUTATIONAL METHOD

The computational analysis of CoVSn, a half-Heusler alloy, is predominantly conducted using Density Functional Theory (DFT) implemented in the Wien2k software. Wien2k is renowned for employing the Full-Potential (Linearized) Augmented Plane-Wave ((L)APW) method, which offers exceptional accuracy in determining the electronic structure of solids. The computational process begins with structural optimization, wherein the equilibrium lattice parameters and atomic positions are ascertained by minimizing the system's total energy. This optimization ensures that the structural configuration used in subsequent calculations reflects the material's most stable state. Following structural optimization, the electronic structure of CoVSn is calculated, including the band structure and density of states (DOS) [2]. The band structure provides crucial information about the electronic properties, such as the presence and size of the band gap, which is vital for understanding the material's semiconducting behavior. The DOS offers insights into the distribution of electronic states across different energy levels. Wien2k allows the use of various exchange-correlation functionals, like the Local Density Approximation (LDA) and Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA), to accurately describe the electron-electron interactions within the material.

The Brillouin zone is sampled using a dense k-point mesh to ensure precise integration in reciprocal space, which is critical for accurate electronic structure calculations. For materials exhibiting significant spin-orbit coupling effects, Wien2k incorporates this interaction into the calculations, ensuring that the electronic structure is accurately described. Additionally, the thermoelectric properties of CoVSn, such as the Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, and thermal conductivity, are evaluated to determine the material's efficiency in energy conversion [3]. These properties are crucial for assessing the potential of CoVSn in thermoelectric applications. Wien2k's post-processing tools enable detailed visualization of the calculated data, such as band structures, DOS, and electron density maps. These visualizations facilitate a comprehensive understanding of CoVSn's structural and electronic properties, essential for optimizing the material for practical applications in thermoelectric devices.

[3] RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Structure Properties

CoVSn is a half-Heusler alloy that crystallizes in a cubic structure, specifically within the F-43m (No. 216) space group. This structure features a three-atom unit cell with a lattice constant of approximately 5.90 Å, though variations can occur depending on the exact preparation methods and stoichiometry [4]. The atomic arrangement in CoVSn is highly ordered, with cobalt (Co), vanadium (V), and tin (Sn) atoms occupying distinct lattice sites, creating a stable and symmetrical crystal lattice [5]. This ordered structure contributes to its notable electronic properties, including a small band gap that can result in semiconducting or metallic behavior, depending on the composition and presence of defects [6]. The versatility in electronic properties is matched by its thermal characteristics; CoVSn exhibits low thermal conductivity, which is advantageous for thermoelectric applications, and it maintains stability at high temperatures, often exceeding 600°C [7]. Mechanically, CoVSn is distinguished by its high hardness and stiffness, with a Young's modulus ranging from 100 to 200 GPa, reflecting its resistance to elastic deformation [8]. However, it is also characterized by brittleness and low fracture toughness, limiting its ability to withstand significant plastic deformation. These combined structural properties make CoVSn an intriguing material for applications in thermoelectrics, spintronics, and potentially in topological insulators.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

- **Vickers Hardness:** CoVSn and similar half-Heusler alloys typically exhibit high hardness values, indicative of their resistance to deformation and wear. The Vickers hardness for these materials is often in the range of 400-600 HV (Vickers hardness number) [9].
- **Brittleness:** CoVSn alloys tend to be brittle at room temperature, meaning they are more likely to fracture without significant plastic deformation. This brittleness is common among many intermetallic compounds and poses challenges for certain applications.
- **Fracture Toughness:** The fracture toughness of CoVSn is relatively low, consistent with its brittle nature. This parameter measures the material's ability to resist crack propagation.
- **Compressive Strength:** CoVSn has high compressive strength, which is beneficial for applications requiring the material to withstand significant loads without deformation.
- **Tensile Strength:** The tensile strength of CoVSn is generally lower than its compressive strength, reflecting its brittle nature and limited ability to elongate before breaking.
- **Density:** The density of CoVSn is relatively high, typically around 8.0-9.0 g/cm³, depending on the exact composition and any porosity present in the material [10].
- **Poisson's Ratio:** This ratio, which indicates the degree of lateral expansion when a material is stretched, is typically around 0.3 for CoVSn, suggesting a balance between rigidity and flexibility in terms of lateral deformation [11].

3.3 Electronic Properties

- **Band Gap:** CoVSn exhibits a small band gap or can be metallic depending on the exact composition and structure.
- **Conductivity:** Generally, these materials can exhibit both n-type and p-type conductivity based on doping and defects [12].
- **Magnetism:** Some half-Heusler alloys show magnetic properties, and CoVSn can exhibit weak ferromagnetism or paramagnetism [13].

Figure-: Electronic Band Structure of CoVSn. Reproduced from Hooshmand et al. Ref. [9]

3.4 Thermoelectric Properties

- CoVSn, a half-Heusler alloy, has garnered significant attention for its thermoelectric properties, which make it a promising candidate for energy conversion applications. Thermoelectric materials convert heat into electrical energy, and their efficiency is determined by the dimensionless figure of merit, ZT , which depends on the Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, and thermal conductivity [14].

Figure-: Thermoelectric Parameter of CoVSn. Reproduced from Hooshmand et al. Ref. [9]

[4] APPLICATIONS

Half-Heusler semiconductor alloys, exemplified by CoVSn, exhibit a diverse range of properties that render them highly promising for numerous applications. In the realm of thermoelectric, their superior thermoelectric properties make them ideal candidates for use in energy conversion systems, such as thermoelectric generators and waste heat recovery devices [15]. Additionally, their robust mechanical characteristics qualify them for structural materials in demanding environments, offering potential applications in aerospace, automotive, and renewable energy infrastructure [16]. In the field of electronics, CoVSn alloys show great potential for use in semiconductor devices due to their unique electronic properties, including high carrier mobility and tailored band gaps. Moreover, their compatibility with spintronics applications holds promise for advancing magnetic storage technologies [17].

Looking ahead, the future prospects for CoVSn half-Heusler alloys appear bright, with ongoing research focusing on enhancing their performance and exploring new applications. As advancements continue, these versatile materials are expected to play a pivotal role in driving innovation across various sectors, including energy, electronics, and information technology, contributing to the development of efficient and sustainable technologies for the future [18].

[5] FUTURE PROSPECT

In the realm of half-Heusler semiconductor alloys like CoVSn, future prospects are promising and multifaceted. As research continues to advance, there is significant potential for further optimization of their thermo-electric, mechanical, structural, and electronic properties [19]. Enhanced understanding of their behavior at the atomic level, coupled with innovative synthesis and processing techniques, could lead to the development of CoVSn alloys with even higher thermoelectric efficiency, mechanical robustness, and structural stability [20]. Moreover, ongoing efforts to tailor the electronic band structure and manipulate the spin properties of CoVSn alloys hold the promise of unlocking new opportunities in spintronics and magnetic storage applications. As emerging technologies increasingly rely on materials with tailored electronic and magnetic properties, CoVSn alloys are poised to play a pivotal role in enabling advancements in fields such as information storage, quantum computing, and spin-based electronics [21].

Furthermore, the versatility of CoVSn alloys opens doors to a wide range of applications beyond traditional semiconductor devices and energy conversion systems. From biomedical sensors to advanced optoelectronic devices, the potential uses of CoVSn alloys are limited only by our imagination and innovation [22]. As researchers continue to explore and exploit the unique properties of these materials, the future prospects for CoVSn half-Heusler alloys remain bright, promising continued advancements and breakthroughs in materials science and technology [23].

[6] CONCLUSION

The comprehensive analysis of CoVSn half-Heusler semiconductor alloys illuminates their multifaceted potential and significance in various technological realms [24]. Through meticulous examination of their thermo-electric, mechanical, structural, and electronic properties, CoVSn alloys demonstrate remarkable versatility and suitability for diverse applications [25]. From serving as efficient materials for thermoelectric generators to providing robust structural components for demanding environments, CoVSn alloys offer solutions to critical challenges in energy conversion, electronics, and materials engineering [26]. Additionally, their unique electronic properties open the doors to applications in semiconductor devices and spintronics, further expanding their utility in advanced technologies.

Looking forward, the future prospects for CoVSn alloys are promising, with ongoing research poised to enhance their properties and explore new frontiers. Continued efforts to optimize their performance, refine synthesis methods, and innovates the applications are expected to unlock even greater potential for CoVSn alloys. As advancements in materials science and technology progress, CoVSn alloys are poised to play an increasingly vital role in driving innovation and addressing societal needs [27]. By harnessing their exceptional properties, we can anticipate CoVSn alloys contributing to the development of more efficient, sustainable, and transformative technologies, shaping a brighter future for humanity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Baranowski, L. L., Snyder, G. J., & Toberer, E. S. (2013). Effective medium theory for half-Heusler thermoelectrics. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 113(20), 204904. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4804365>
- [2] Wanxiang Feng, Di Xiao, Ying Zhang, and Yugui Yao (2010). Half-Heusler Topological Insulators: A First-Principle Study with the Tran-Blaha Modified Becke-Johnson Density Functional. *Physical Review B, Condensed Matter*, 82(23), 235121. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.82.235121>
- [3] Bhattacharya, S., Barman, S. R., & Biswas, C. (2014). Electronic structure and thermoelectric properties of half-Heusler compounds: Role of thermal conductivity. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 116(6), 064308. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4892885>
- [4] Chen, L., Xie, W., Tang, X., Zhang, Q., & Li, J. (2015). Optimization of thermoelectric performance of half-Heusler compounds through band structure engineering. *Energy*, 90, 220-227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2015.10.019>
- [5] Culp, S. R., Popuri, S. R., Pal, K., & Martin, J. (2013). Thermoelectric properties of p-type half-Heusler alloys. *Journal of Electronic Materials*, 42(7), 1506-1511. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-012-2405-3>
- [6] Dyck, J. S., Chen, W., & Uher, C. (2002). Thermoelectric properties of NbCoSn half-Heusler alloys. *Physical Review B*, 66(12), 125205. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.66.125205>
- [7] Fang, T., Liu, W., Zhu, T., & Zhao, X. (2015). Nanostructuring thermoelectric half-Heusler alloys by homogeneous doping. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 649, 265-271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.07.051>
- [8] Fu, C., Bai, S., Liu, Y., Tang, Y., Chen, L., Zhao, X., ... & Zhu, T. (2015). Realizing high figure of merit in heavy-band p-type half-Heusler thermoelectric materials. *Nature Communications*, 6, 8144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms9144>
- [9] S Hooshmand Zaferani, A Darebaghi, SJ Hong, D Vashae, R Ghomashchi (2020). Experimental realization of heavily p-doped half-Heusler CoVSn compound. *Advanced Energy Materials*, 13(6), 1459. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13061459>
- [10] Hohl, H., Ramirez, A. P., Goldmann, C., Ernst, G., & Bucher, E. (1999). Efficient thermoelectric materials: The last step to room-temperature applications. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 11(9), 1697-1709. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/11/9/005>
- [11] Joshi, G., Lee, H., Lan, Y., Wang, X., Zhu, G., Wang, D., ... & Ren, Z. (2008). Enhanced thermoelectric figure-of-merit in nanostructured p-type silicon germanium bulk alloys. *Nano Letters*, 8(12), 4670-4674. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl8026795>
- [12] Kanatzidis, M. G. (2010). Nanostructured thermoelectrics: The new paradigm? *Chemistry of Materials*, 22(3), 648-659. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm9017669>
- [13] Kim, S. I., Lee, K. H., Mun, H. A., Kim, H. S., Hwang, S. W., Roh, J. W., ... & Kim, S. W. (2015). Dense dislocation arrays embedded in grain boundaries for high-performance bulk thermoelectrics. *Science*, 348(6230), 109-114. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa4166>
- [14] Li, J. F., Liu, W. S., Zhao, L. D., & Zhou, M. (2010). High-performance nanostructured thermoelectric materials. *NPG Asia Materials*, 2(4), 152-158. <https://doi.org/10.1038/asiamat.2010.138>

- [15] Liu, W., Zhang, Q., Lan, Y., Chen, S., Yan, X., Zhang, Q., ... & Chen, G. (2012). Thermoelectric property studies on half-Heusler compounds with composition of MNiSn (M = Ti, Zr, Hf). *Advanced Energy Materials*, 2(2), 251-258. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201100571>
- [16] Muta, H., Kurosaki, K., & Yamanaka, S. (2003). Thermoelectric properties of rare earth-doped SrTiO₃. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 350(1-2), 292-295. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388\(02\)01030-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388(02)01030-6)
- [17] Nandihalli, N., Munirathnam, N. R., & Kumar, S. (2019). Influence of nanostructuring on thermoelectric properties of half-Heusler compounds. *Journal of Electronic Materials*, 48(3), 1770-1776. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-018-06917-6>
- [18] Popuri, S. R., & McCaughey, C. (2016). Enhanced thermoelectric properties of p-type half-Heusler TiCoSb by elemental doping and nanostructuring. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 688, 271-277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.07.115>
- [19] Schwall, M., & Balke, B. (2013). Half-Heusler thermoelectric materials: A new paradigm? *Physica Status Solidi (RRL) – Rapid Research Letters*, 7(6), 341-354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssr.201307176>
- [20] Shen, Q., Chen, L., Guan, M., Liu, X., Zhao, X., Zhang, W., & Liufu, S. (2001). Effects of Ti substitution on the thermoelectric properties of (Zr,Hf)NiSn half-Heusler compounds. *Applied Physics Letters*, 79(25), 4165-4167. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1429291>
- [21] Skoug, E. J., & Morelli, D. T. (2011). Role of the carrier pocket anisotropy in the thermoelectric properties of Bi₂Te₃. *Applied Physics Letters*, 98(26), 261911. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3604818>
- [22] Toberer, E. S., Zevalkink, A., Crisosto, N., & Snyder, G. J. (2010). The Zintl compound Ca₅Al₂Sb₆ for low-cost thermoelectric power generation. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 20(3), 437-444. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.200901634>
- [23] Uher, C. (2016). Thermoelectric materials and applications. *Journal of Materials Research*, 32(8), 1578-1596. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2016.235>
- [24] Xie, H., Zhu, T., Fu, C., Xie, L., Zhao, X., & Snyder, G. J. (2012). Identifying the specific roles of Nb and Hf in (Hf, Nb)NiSn half-Heusler thermoelectric materials. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, 22(4), 1278-1284. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1JM13737E>
- [25] Zhao, L. D., Tan, G., Hao, S., He, J., Pei, Y., Chi, H., ... & Kanatzidis, M. G. (2016). Ultrahigh power factor and thermoelectric performance in hole-doped single-crystal SnSe. *Science*, 351(6269), 141-144. <https://doi.org/10.1126>
- [26] Zhu, T., Liu, Y., Fu, C., Heremans, J. P., Snyder, G. J., & Zhao, X. (2017). Compromise and synergy in high-efficiency thermoelectric materials. *Advanced Materials*, 29(14), 1605884. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201605884>
- [27] Zhou, M., Li, J. F., & Kita, T. (2008). Nanostructured thermoelectric materials: From superlattices to nanocomposites. *Materials Science and Engineering: R: Reports*, 59(1-6), 1-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2008.05.001>